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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Bilayer Tablets of Teneligliptin by Using Liquid Solid Compact Technology

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ABSTRACT

Teneligliptin is an antidiabetic medication and belongs to BCS class II drugs. The present study aims at the preparation of liquisolid compact of teneligliptin with an aim to improve the solubility of the drug. The liquid solid system uses a non-volatile solvent to dissolve the drug. The drug's suspension or solution is transformed into a free-flowing, dry, and compressible powder by mixing it with a statistically determined amount of coating and carrier material. In this study Microcrystalline cellulose and Aerosil were used as carrier and coating material respectively. The non-volatile solvent that was used is propylene glycol. Nine formulations with varying excipient ratios were created, and their flowability and compressibility were assessed. A study on the interaction between drugs and excipients was conducted using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The optimized formulations were evaluated for flowability, compressibility study, comparative dissolution study with pure drug. The improved formulations exhibited good compression characteristics and flow properties. The medication and excipient did not physically interact, according to the FTIR analysis. The comparative dissolution study of the optimized formulations with the pure drug revealed significant improvement of solubility of teneligliptin in liquid solid compact. The diffusion exponent (n) of Korsmeyer-peppas model was found to be non-fickian. The results showed that liquid solid had illustrated significantly higher drug release rates than those of expectedly made was due to an increment in wetting properties and surface of sedate accessible for disintegration. Therefore, it can be concluded that a free flowing, non-adherent, dry and compressible powder of teneligliptin can be prepared using liquid solid compact technology.

INTRODUCTION

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Liquisolid compact technology is found to be successful tool to improve solubility and dissolution of poorly water-soluble drugs and ultimately its bioavailability. The term "liquid solid system" describes formulations that are created by combining drug solution or suspension with a chosen carrier and coating material to transform liquid drug, drug suspension, or medication solution in non-volatile solvents into a powder combination that is dry, non-adherent, free-flowing, and compressible with ease. The liquisolid technique involves dissolving the drug in the liquid medium and incorporating it into a carrier material, such as cellulose, that has a porous surface and closely matted fibers inside. This results in both adsorption and absorption of the drug. The liquid is first taken up by the internal structure of the particles and absorbed there. Both absorption and adsorption occur when a carrier

material, such as cellulose, with a porous surface and closely matted fibre inside, is coupled with the medication dissolved in the liquid vehicle. The particles inside surface retains the liquid that was first absorbed inside of it. Adsorption of the liquid onto the porous carrier particle's interior and exterior surfaces happens after saturation. Then, coating material provides the desirable flow property to the liquidsolid system due to its high adsorptive properties and large surface area.

MATERIALS AND EQUIPMENTS

Materials: - Tenueligiptin was received as a gift sample from Metro chem. And HPMC, Propylene Glycol, Sodium starch glycolate, Aerosil and Microcrystalline cellulose all other chemicals were of analytical grade.

Equipment

Table 1: - List of Equipment

S.no	Equipment / Instruments
1.	Digital weighing balance
2.	UV spectrophotometer
3.	FTIR
4.	Friability tester
5.	Hardness tester
6.	pH meter
7.	Tablet compression machine
8.	Disintegration Test Apparatus USP
9.	Dissolution Test apparatus USP

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Preformulation study:

1.Preparation Of Standard Calibration Curve: Tenueligiptin spectrophotometric techniques in UV

Preparation of 0.1N HCl: -To make 0.1 N HCl, 8.5 ml of hydrochloric acid was diluted to 1000 ml with water.

Determination of λ_{max} : The λ_{max} U.V spectrum of tenueligiptin was measured in 0.1N HCl. Tenueligiptin with an exact weight of 10 mg was

transferred to a 100.0 ml volumetric flask, to which 30 ml of 0.1 N HCl was added. The mixture was then ultrasonicated for 10 minutes, and the volume was adjusted with 0.1 N HCl (100 μ g/ml). The final concentration of Tenueligiptin was achieved by diluting the standard stock solution with 0.1 N HCl. After that, the solution was scanned in spectrum mode in a 1.0 cm column against 0.1 N HCl as a blank, ranging from 400 nm to 200 nm. The maximum absorption wavelength (λ_{max}) is typically around 243 nm.

Construction of calibration curve: -

Teneligliptin at an exact weight of 10 mg was added to a 100.0 ml volumetric flask along with 30 ml of 0.1 N HCl and ultrasonicated for 10 minutes. The volume was then adjusted with 100 µg/ml of 0.1 N HCl. Aliquot portions of 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, and 5.0 ml were diluted to 10.0 ml using 0.1 N HCl (concentration 0, 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 µg/l, respectively) from the standard stock solution. At 243 nm, the absorbances of diluted solutions were measured using 0.1 N hydrochloric acid as a blank.

2. Solubility study of teneligliptin in various solvents

The solubility of Teneligliptin in methanol and two liquid vehicles tried to prepare the liquid-solid systems, namely, water, tweens & spans, Polyethylene glycol 300, 400, 600, and Propylene glycol were investigated by making saturated drug solutions in these solvents and using spectrophotometry to measure the drug's concentration.

3. FTIR Compatibility studies

FTIR spectroscopy helps to determine any chemical interaction between drug and excipients used in the formulation. FTIR spectra of pure Teneligliptin and physical mixes were obtained using Shimadzu, Japan. Samples are prepared in KBr disks (2mg sample in 200mg KBr). Spectrophotometer operating in the 4000-400 cm⁻¹ range.

4. Flowable Liquid-Retention Potential (Φ-Value) Of the Excipients (Aerosil): -

a) Determination of the angle of slide: -

The angle of slide carrier and coating material 10 gm of Aerosil 200 is measured as follows

Determination of the angle of the slide is done by weighing the required amount of carrier material and placed at one end of a metal plate with a polished surface. The end is gradually elevated until the plate is angled in relation to the horizontal, the point at which the powder is set to

slide. The angle of the slide is the name given to this angle. An angle of 33° is thought to be ideal.

b) Determination of flowable liquid-retention potential (φ-value)

The "flowable liquid-retention potential" (φ -value) of a powder material is its ability to retain a specific amount of liquid while maintaining ideal flow properties. The greatest weight of liquid that can be kept per unit weight of the powder material to create a liquid/powder admixture that flows satisfactorily is known as the Π-value.

The Φ values are calculated according to the equation

$$\Phi \text{ value} = \frac{\text{weight of the liquid}}{\text{weight of solid}} \times 100$$

The Φ-values are plotted graphically against the corresponding angles of slide (h).

The Φ-value corresponding to an angle of slide of 33° represented the flowable liquid-retention potential of excipients. The Φ-value for carrier and coating material is reported in the table below and hence there is no need to determine it practically.

Table 2: Φ-values for carrier material and coating material

Nonvolatile liquid vehicle	Values for carrier material	Values for coating material
Propylene glycol	0.15	2.31
Poly ethylene glycol 400	0.03	3.06
Poly ethylene glycol 600	0.19	1.95
Tween 80	0.12	2.80
Span 20	0.14	0.50

5. Procedure for preparation of liquid-solid system:

1. The model drug is first distributed in liquid vehicles with varying drug:vehicle ratios in non-volatile solvent systems (propylene glycol).
2. Then a mixture of carrier (Microcrystalline cellulose) was added to the above liquid by Continuous mixing for a period of 10 to 20 minutes in a mortar.

3. Then to the above mixture coating material (Aerosil powder) was added and mixed thoroughly. The R value determined how much carrier and coating material was added.

4. To the above binary mixture disintegrant like cross povidone and other additives such as Glidant (magnesium stearate) are added according to their application and mixed in a mortar.

5. The final blend was compressed.

Fig 1: Preparation Liquid-solid compact

6. Formulation Of Teneligliptin Bilayer Tablets

IR Blend

Table 3: - Formulation table of Teneligliptin Immediate release layer

Formulations	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Drug teneligliptin	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Propylene glycol	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
drug conc.in PEC (%w/w)	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
W	120								
L _F	0.6	0.571	0.545	0.533	0.521	0.510	0.5	0.48	0.461
R	5:01	10:01	15:01	5:01	10:01	15:01	5:01	10:01	15:01
MCC (mg) carrier	200	210	220	225	230	235	240	250	260
Aerosil (mg) coating material	20	21	14	45	23	15	48	25	16
Sodium starch glycolate	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
total tablet weight (mg)	370	381	384	420	403	400	438	425	426

SR Blend

Table 4: - Formulation table of Teneligliptin Sustained release layer

Formulations	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Drug teneligliptin	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Propylene glycol	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
drug conc.in PEC (%w/w)	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
W	120								
L _F	0.6	0.571	0.545	0.533	0.521	0.510	0.5	0.48	0.461
R	5:01	10:01	15:01	5:01	10:01	15:01	5:01	10:01	15:01

MCC (mg) carrier	200	210	220	225	230	235	240	250	260
Aerosil (mg) coating material	20	21	14	45	23	15	48	25	16
HPMC	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
total tablet weight (mg)	370	381	384	420	403	400	438	425	426

7. Evaluation Of Powder Blend

The powder blend that was prepared was evaluated using techniques recommended by the Indian Pharmacopoeia, including bulk density, tapped density, Hausner's ratio, angle of repose, and car's index.

- a) **Bulk density:** Teneligliptin's bulk density was determined by carefully adding 5.00g to 20 ml measuring cylinder via a glass funnel. The samples' occupied volumes were noted. The bulk density was computed using the following formula.

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{\text{Weight of sample in grams}}{\text{Volume occupied by the sample}}$$

- b) **Tapped density:** The tapped density was ascertained using the LABINDIA density tester, which consists of a graded cylinder, fixed on a mechanical tapping mechanism. The tapped density was computed using the following formula.

$$\text{Tapped density} = \frac{\text{Weight of sample in grams}}{\text{Tapped volume}}$$

Table No 6: Flow property: (Relation of flow property with HR&CI)

Compressibility Index (%)	Flow Character	Hausner's Ratio
10	Excellent	1.00–1.11
11–15	Good	1.12–1.18
16–20	Fair	1.19–1.25
21–25	Passable	1.26–1.34
26–31	Poor	1.35–1.45
32–37	Very poor	1.46–1.59

- c) **Compressibility Index and Hausner's ratio:** The compressibility index and Hausner's ratio were computed utilizing the bulk thickness and the tapped thickness of a powder.

$$\text{Carr's index} = \frac{\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density}}{\text{Tapped density}}$$

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$$

- d) **Angle of repose:** The equation was used to determine the angle of repose and the diameter of the powder cone.

$$\tan\theta = h/r$$

where h and r stand for the pile's height and radius, respectively.

Table No 5: The relation between angle of repose and flow properties

Angle of repose θ	Flow
<25	Excellent
25-30	Good
30-40	Passible
>40	Very poor

>38	Very, very poor	>1.60
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8. Evaluation of tablets: (Postcompression Parameter)

1. Weight variation
2. Thickness
3. Hardness
4. Assay of formulations
5. Friability
6. Disintegration Time
7. Dissolution
8. Stability studies

1. **Weight Variation:** A random selection of twenty tablets was weighed, and the average weight was ascertained. The specific weight of each pill was determined. According to USP regulations, no tablet weight may be less than 90% or more than 110% of the average weight.
2. **Thickness:** Three tablets are randomly selected from each formulation and thickness is measured individually by vernier caliper. It is expressed in millimeter (mm) and average is calculated.
3. **Hardness:** Take 10 tablets containing the substance that was provided for analysis. Calculate the Hardness in kg/cm² for every tablet and note the results. Determine the average result by averaging the ten measurements.

Acceptance criteria: Not less than 4.0Kg/cm²

4. **Friability (core tablets):** Take thirteen tablets from the sample that was provided for analysis and dedusting. Once the tablets have been weighed, note the outcome. Once the tablets have been inserted into the drum of the friability equipment, turn the device on for four minutes, or one hundred rotations. Run the device for the specified duration or rpm. After taking out the tablets, dust off.

Weigh the tablets and calculate the friability by the following formulae.

$$\text{Friability (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Initial weight of the tablets} - \text{Final weight of the tablets})}{\text{Initial weight of the tablets}} \times 100$$

Acceptance criteria: Friability is not more than 1.0%

5. **Assay of the Formulations:** - The total amount of drug present in the liquisolid formulation is evaluated using UV spectrophotometric analysis. Approximately weighed quantity of 10mg equivalent of drug is taken from liquisolid formulation which is dissolved in 10ml of methanol and the volume is made upto 100ml with distilled water. From the above solution, 10 ml is taken and diluted with distilled water. The absorbance of resulting solution (10µg/ml) is measured at 234 nm using spectrophotometer (shimadzu UV- 1700 pharma spec, Japan) and the drug content is calculated from the standard curve using the formula

$$\text{Drug content} = \frac{\text{Sample absorbance}}{\text{Standard absorbance}} \times 100$$

6. **Disintegration Time:** Wait for a bit for the temperature to reach the required 37⁰C after turning on the device and adding water to the beakers. When the temperature reaches the appropriate level, the alarm will sound on the device. Place each basket case with the six tablets. Press the start button to initiate the disintegration process, and then observe the tablets disappear. Note how long it took for the last tablet to dissolve entirely (no tablet pieces should remain on the mesh covers of the basket).

Acceptance criteria: Not more than 30 minutes.

7. **Dissolution Studies (In Vitro-Drug Release Studies):** Using a USP-type 2 (paddle type) device in a sink situation, the model drug

release from various formulations was ascertained. The dissolving medium used 900ml of Phosphate buffer of pH 6.8 at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and 50 rpm. For two hours, the prepared mixture was put through dissolving tests. At predefined intervals (30min,1,2,4,6,8,10, and 12 hours), a 5-milliliter sample was removed, filtered using Whatman filter paper, and replaced with an equivalent volume of dissolving liquid. The UV spectrophotometer was used to measure the amount of drug present in the dissolution sample at 243 nm.

8. **Stability studies:** The best formulation of three batches is stored at $36^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and relative RH $75\% \pm 5\%$ for three months. The

best formulation is evaluated using dissolution test, drug content, physical appearance, hardness and thickness. The above tests of best formulations are compared with those of freshly prepared tablets. The results showed no significant changes in physical appearance, hardness, thickness, drug content and dissolution test of aged tablets compared to the fresh liquisolid tablets. This indicates that the liquisolid tablets were stable under these storage conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1.Preformulation studies: Pure drug is a white solid that has no odor and slightly bitter taste

2.UV analysis of Teneligliptin: -Absorption maxima (λ_{max}) was found to be 243nm

Fig 2: Spectrum of Teneligliptin pure drug

- 3. Calibration curve of Teneligliptin:** -When examined in the range of 200 nm to 400 nm, Teneligliptin showed an absorption maximum [λ_{max}] at 243nm. A 0.1N HCL solution was produced with varying concentrations, and the

absorbance values at λ_{max} (243 nm) were recorded. The calibration curves displayed a correlation coefficient of $R^2 = 0.999$

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Fig 3: Standard curve of Teneligliptin pure drug

Table 7: Calibration curve values of Teneligliptin

Sr. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance at 243 nm
1	0	0
2	2	0.067
3	4	0.141
4	6	0.225
5	8	0.299
6	10	0.382

4. Drug Excipient compatibility studies: -The compatibility of pharmacological excipients was investigated using the FTIR spectrophotometer. Teneligliptin and the utilized

excipients did not appear to interact, according to FTIR data for both the medicine taken alone and in combination with the excipients.

Fig 4: FTIR Spectrum of Teneligliptin

Fig 5: FTIR Spectrum of Teneiglipitin + Propylene glycol

Fig 6: - FTIR Spectrum of Teneiglipitin + Microcrystalline cellulose

Fig 7: - FTIR Spectrum of Teneiglipitin + Aerosil

Fig 8: - FTIR Spectrum of Teneligliptin + Sodium starch glycolate

Fig 9: - FTIR Spectrum of Teneligliptin + Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose

Infrared (IR) spectroscopic studies were carried out to confirm the compatibility between drug and excipients used for the preparation of liquid tablets. The IR studies were performed for teneligliptin (pure drug), non-volatile liquid vehicle, microcrystalline cellulose, Aerosil 200 and physical mixture of drug and excipients. The spectra observed at 4000cm⁻¹ to 400 cm⁻¹

Table 8: - Drug's FTIR compatibility with various excipients

Functional group	N-H	C-H	C-C	C-S
Reference peak wave number	3170-3500	2800-3000	1300-800	800-1070
Teneligliptin pure drug	3324.2	2923.7	1324.5	968.9

Teneligliptin + Propylene glycol	3324.6	2955.3	1327.9	960.2
Teneligliptin+ MCC	3323.9	2953.2	1324.8	969.8
Teneligliptin+ Aerosil	3336.7	2952.9	1338.7	971.9
Teneligliptin+ Sodium starch glycolate	3435.5	2953.2	1356.2	971.5
Teneligliptin+ HPMC	3434.8	2952.9	1326.4	971.6

The principal peaks for pure drug were observed at wave numbers 3324.2 cm⁻¹, 2923.7 cm⁻¹, 1324.5 cm⁻¹ and 968.9 cm⁻¹, Further in the physical mixtures, all the above characteristics peaks of the medication show up in the spectrum, indicating that the medicine and polymers in the physical combination did not interact. All of the aforementioned peaks in the pure drug's spectrum also show in the physical mixes, indicating that there was no interaction between the drug and polymers.

5. Solubility study of Teneligliptin in various solvents

The solubility of Teneligliptin was determined in various nonvolatile liquid vehicles such as Propylene glycol (PG), Polyethylene glycol (PEG 600,300,200), Tween (80,85), Span (20,80), Methanol and Polysorbate 80. From the results, it was observed that the solubility of drug in Propylene glycol was higher when compared with other liquid vehicles which may be due to the high viscosity and HLB value

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Fig 10: Graph of solubility studies of Teneligliptin
Table 9: - Solubility study values of teneligliptin

	Sample ID	Type	Ex	Conc	WL243.0
1	Peg 600	Unknown		37.590	1.470
2	Tween 80	Unknown		33.238	1.298
3	Span 80	Unknown		34.332	1.341
4	Tween 85	Unknown		30.164	1.177
5	Peg 300	Unknown		43.114	1.688
6	P glycol	Unknown		39.114	1.530
7	Methanol	Unknown		42.219	1.653

8	Peg 200	Unknown		42.065	1.647
9	Polysorbate 80	Unknown		38.574	1.509
10	Span 20	Unknown		32.655	1.275
11					

6. Precompression Studies – Flow Properties

The blend's bulk density was discovered to range from 0.18 – 0.39 grams per ml. The range of tapped density was 0.21 – 0.45 g/ml. Hausner's ratio and Carr's index were computed based on these values, respectively. The results show that all of the

formulations had good flow character. The formulations exhibited an angle of repose of 23° to 31°, signifying that the material possessed exceptional flow characteristics, making the blends appropriate for direct compression

Table 11: - Flow properties of the blend

Formulation	Angle of repose	Bulk density (gm/ml)	Tapped Density (gm/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio
IR BLEND					
F1	27 ± 0.25	0.19 ± 0.02	0.22± 0.04	13.63± 0.12	1.15± 0.10
F2	30± 0.22	0.22± 0.08	0.25± 0.03	12.00± 0.29	1.13± 0.13
F3	23± 0.24	0.23± 0.05	0.26± 0.02	11.53± 0.19	1.13± 0.22
F4	26± 0.11	0.21± 0.01	0.23± 0.01	8.69± 0.17	1.09± 0.19
F5	29± 0.19	0.24± 0.07	0.28± 0.06	14.28± 0.21	1.16± 0.18
F6	31± 0.22	0.18± 0.09	0.21± 0.05	10.00± 0.15	1.11± 0.15
F7	29± 0.26	0.25± 0.01	0.29± 0.09	13.79± 0.22	1.16± 0.22
F8	26± 0.32	0.29± 0.03	0.33± 0.08	12.12± 0.22	1.13± 0.21
F9	27± 0.29	0.27± 0.04	0.31± 0.07	12.90± 0.44	1.14± 0.12
SR BLEND					
F1	27±0.27	0.36±0.033	0.41±0.032	12.19±0.11	1.138±0.010
F2	25±0.26	0.37±0.031	0.42±0.019	11.90±0.17	1.135±0.028
F3	28±0.12	0.36±0.029	0.40±0.034	10.00±0.36	1.111±0.010
F4	27±0.37	0.38±0.012	0.43±0.021	11.62±0.17	1.131±0.025
F5	25±0.25	0.39±0.018	0.45±0.018	13.33±0.12	1.153±0.037
F6	24±0.24	0.33±0.024	0.38±0.025	13.15±0.26	1.151±0.032
F7	26±0.29	0.34±0.019	0.39±0.029	12.82±0.17	1.147±0.018
F8	25±0.22	0.35±0.012	0.39±0.024	10.25±0.26	1.114±0.029
F9	23±0.23	0.37±0.010	0.43±0.019	13.95±0.12	1.162±0.031

7. Evaluation Of Experimental Batch:

Table displays the data gathered from the post-compression of core tablets, including weight variation, thickness, hardness, friability, and disintegration test. The weight variation test was passed by all core tablet formulations since the weight variation ranged from 738 – 890 mg Which is within pharmacopeial standards. The hardness of the core tablets, which ranged from 5.34 to

10.5 kg/cm², was determined to be homogeneous and acceptable across batch variations. All of the formulations F1 through F9 core tablet thicknesses (3.38 – 5.87mm) were found to be adequate, guaranteeing the mechanical stability of each formulation. Friability values were determined to be less than 0.8% in all six formulations (F1 through F9), and each formulation was deemed to be satisfactory.

Table 12: - Evaluation of post compression parameters of optimized formulation

Formulation	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Weight Variation (mg)	Friability (%)	Disintegration time (min)
F1	5.34	3.38	738±3.6	1.14	2.29 ±0.20
F2	6.42	4.54	761±3.0	0.62	4.27 ±0.17
F3	8.3	4.98	772±4.7	0.43	4.89 ±0.27
F4	7.52	6.23	841±4.5	0.57	3.87 ±0.18
F5	9.25	5.87	803±3.0	0.48	5.78 ±0.21
F6	7.36	5.34	800±4.5	0.61	4.63 ±0.36
F7	10.5	4.92	870±2.0	0.32	6.67 ±0.22
F8	9.41	4.17	854±3.5	0.46	5.78 ± 0.42
F9	8.33	5.85	857±3.6	0.64	± 0.17

❖ Drug Content

The percentage Teneligliptin content of all formulations varied between 97%- 102%

Table 13: Assay of teneligliptin Bilayer tablets

Formulations	Drug content (%)
F 1	98.8 ±0.42
F 2	99.5 ±0.23
F 3	97.8 ±0.26
F 4	95.2 ± 0.33
F 5	102.2 ±0.10
F 6	97.0 ±0.71
F 7	96.5 ±0.81
F 8	96.9 ±0.71
F 9	106.2 ±0.87

8. Dissolution studies of Teneligliptin Bilayer tablets

Table 14: - Dissolution study of Teneligliptin Bilayer Tablets

Time (hrs)	%CDR	%CDR	%CDR	%CDR
	F1	F2	F3	F4
0	0	0	0	0
30min	5.87±1.23	6.52±1.39	4.78±1.74	7.87±1.43
1	10.23±2.04	14.32±1.34	12.98±2.14	16.76±3.25
2	18.87±1.05	33.65±2.09	22.23±2.32	38.34±1.83
4	27.63±1.47	52.78±2.55	29.83± 3.61	42.43±2.64
6	32.98±2.10	65.29±1.56	37.89±2.20	51.85±0.72
8	50.85±1.90	74.52±0.88	44.73±1.88	69.59±1.34
10	58.69±2.74	86.55±2.36	60.85±0.73	74.36±2.43
12	70.64±3.78	99.89±0.94	68.5±1.53	81.94±1.32

Table 15: - Dissolution study of Teneligliptin Bilayer Tablets

Time (hrs)	%CDR	%CDR	%CDR	%CDR	%CDR
	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9

0	0	0	0	0	0
30min	5.98±0.37	4.12±2.83	7.32±1.33	8.92±4.65	3.46±0.56
1	19.46±1.21	20.48±1.95	21.72±2.73	13.98±4.23	21.36±1.69
2	28.82±2.54	29.98±0.53	27.89±1.32	29.43±2.87	35.78±4.23
4	39.65±1.63	43.12±2.65	42.36±0.87	41.36±2.55	50.01±1.76
6	58.87±2.01	50.25±0.67	60.88±1.61	58.18±1.87	62.14±2.34
8	64.92±1.02	71.42±1.54	68.32±0.62	70.54±1.92	69.94±3.54
10	69.63±2.43	76.84±1.73	73.01±1.66	83.4±2.75	78.14±1.76
12	78.95±1.52	82.84±2.74	90.1±2.63	97.12±2.43	83.94±2.65

Fig 11: %CDR VS TIME

According to Tables 14,15 and Figure 11, Formulations F1, F4 and F7 were prepared with 1:10, (ratio of drug and Propylene glycol) (ratio of MCC & Aerosil 200) showed the cumulative % of drug release 95.64%, 95.94%, and 93.1% respectively.

Formulations F3, F5, F8 were prepared with 1:10, (ratio of drug and Propylene glycol) (ratio of MCC & Aerosil 200) showed the cumulative % of drug release 99.89%, 97.95% and 99.12% respectively.

Formulations F2, F5, F9 were prepared with 1:10, (ratio of drug and Propylene glycol) 15:1, (ratio of MCC & Aerosil 200) showed the cumulative % of drug release 94.5%,96.84% and 97.94% respectively.

F2 (99.89%) was the formulation with the highest release of all the formulations.

9. Comparison Between Pure Drug and Formulation

Table 16: - Drug release of improved formulation and Pure drug

Time in Hours	% CDR F2	PURE DRUG
0	0	0
0.5	6.52±1.39	2.89±0.22
1	14.32±1.34	8.54±2.09
2	33.65±2.09	13.63±1.42
4	52.78±2.55	29.82±1.04
6	65.29±1.56	36.99±1.35

8	74.52±0.88	39.73±0.98
10	86.55±2.36	52.77±2.67
12	99.89±0.94	69.84±1.84

Fig 12: - Drug release of Optimized formulation VS Pure drug

- Comparatively Optimized formulation of Teneeligiptin made by liquidsolid compact technology showed better drug release than pure drug

10. Drug Release Kinetics Study

Table 17: - Drug release kinetics

Time in Hours	% CDR	Log % CDR	% Cumulative Drug Remaining	Log % Cumulative Drug Remaining	Square Root of Time	Log T	Cube root of CDR
0	0	0	99.89	1.999	0	0	0
0.5	6.52	0.814	93.37	1.970	0.707	-0.301	1.868
1	14.32	1.155	85.57	1.932	1	0	2.428
2	33.65	1.526	66.24	1.821	1.414	0.301	3.228
4	52.78	1.722	47.11	1.673	2	0.602	3.751
6	65.29	1.814	34.6	1.539	2.449	0.778	4.026
8	74.52	1.872	25.37	1.404	2.828	0.903	4.208
10	86.55	1.937	13.34	1.125	3.162	1	4.423
12	99.89	1.999	0	0	3.464	1.0791	4.639

Fig 13: - Zero order kinetics

Fig 14: - First order kinetics

Fig 15: - Higuchi plot

Fig 16: - Korsmeyer Peppas Plot

Drug Release Kinetics

Table 18: Drug Release Kinetics Results

Formulation	2
Zero order R2	0.9584
First Order R2	0.9296
Higuchi R2	0.9658
Korsmeyer Peppas R2	0.984

11. Stability studies

The stability studies were investigated whether the physical chemical parameters and dissolution of liquid solid tablets is affected by storage under 36° C ± 2° C and relative RH 75% ± 5% for three months. The results showed no significant changes

in physical appearance, hardness, thickness, drug content and dissolution test of aged tablets compared to the fresh liquid solid tablets. This suggests that under these storage circumstances, the liquid solid pills remained stable.

Table 19: - Short term stabilities of Optimized formulation

Parameters	initial	1 st month	2 nd month	3 rd month
Appearance	Good	Good	Good	Good
Average weight (mg)	781±3.0	781±3.0	780±3.0	780±3.0
Thickness (mm)	4.54	4.54	4.54	4.40
Hardness (kg/cm ²)	6.42	6.42	6.42	6.42
% Friability	0.62	0.60	0.60	0.58
Disintegration (sec)	4.27 ±0.17	4.27 ±0.17	4.27 ±0.17	4.27 ±0.17
In vitro Dissolution (CDR)	99.89	99.44	98.76	98.12

CONCLUSION

In this study, a novel formulation termed as liquid-solid compacts was created by combining API

with excipients. Drug excipient compatibility studies verified that Teneligliptin and the other excipients chosen for the formulation were compatible. Precompression factors such as bulk density, tapped density, and Hausner's ratio were assessed for the prepared blend. Following this, post compression parameters such as thickness, hardness, friability, disintegration, and dissolving were assessed for the tablets. After evaluating each formulation, the optimal formulation, identified as formulation F2, was used to load the batch for stability at accelerated stability conditions $36^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and relative RH $75\% \pm 5\%$ for three months. The formulation passed the evaluations. Thus, it was determined that the formulation's drug release profile was superior. This innovative formulation strategy could be beneficial for increasing bioavailability.

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